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Research Article

**STATE REGULATION AND ENTERPRISES PERFORMANCE
SUPPORT INTO TOURISM AND RECREATION FIELD**Sergey Kosarin¹, Irina Milkina¹, Olga Badlaeva², Danara Idzhilova², Elena Egorinova²¹Moscow State University of Management, Moscow, Russia, ²Kalmyk State University named after B. B. Gorodovikov, Elista, Russia.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

The article describes the main documents regulating the state regulation of the tourism industry in the Republic of Kalmykia, analyzes the tourism potential of the region and the dynamics of the development of tourism and recreation services. The development of tourism and recreation in the territory can serve as one of the tools to combat the main socio-economic problems and increase the competitiveness of the regional economy.

Revealing the tourist potential, the republic will get the opportunity to develop business in this direction, which is an important factor in the process of attracting new money flows and investments in the economy. It is the development of the tourism industry on the territory of the Republic of Kalmykia that can serve as one of the tools to combat major socio-economic problems, ensure the creation of new jobs and expand the sphere of small and medium-sized businesses, lead to a reduction in the outflow of able-bodied young people, as well as provide prerequisites for improved competitiveness. economy of the region.

Key words: *state regulation, tourism, region, domestic tourism, competitiveness.*

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INTRODUCTION:

State regulation in any sphere consists in the interaction of state and regional authorities, their influence on the activities of economic entities, market conditions, living standards and population structure.

Today, the tourism industry due to the strong state support is rapidly developing and is one of the most promising sectors of the world economy, which has a large-scale multiplier effect and a serious impact on all sectors of the economy.

The state authorities, in turn, recognizing the tourist activity of one of the most priority sectors of the economy, performs the following strategic tasks:

- promotion of tourism activities and the creation of favorable conditions for development;
- formation and support of priority tourist activities;
- formation of an attractive tourist “image”;
- support of tour operators, travel agents and their associations.

During the period of Western sanctions against the Russian Federation, inflation, the state sent its forces to the development of domestic tourism. A promising tourism industry is the development of this activity in the Republic of Kalmykia, which will affect tax revenues to the state budget, will promote the development of small and medium-sized businesses, attract private investment, and create additional jobs. State regulation of the tourism industry in the Republic of Kalmykia is carried out through the implementation of the following basic documents:

- Federal Target Program for the Development of the Tourist Complex “Development of Domestic and Inbound Tourism in the Russian Federation for 2011-2018”;
- State program of the Republic of Kalmykia “Development of culture and tourism of the Republic of Kalmykia for 2013-2020”
- “The concept of development of ethnocultural tourism in the Republic of Kalmykia for 2015-2018.”
- The main federal target program for the development of the tourist complex is the program “Development of domestic and inbound tourism in the Russian Federation for 2011-2018”, which is designed to increase the competitiveness of the domestic tourist market, as well as create conditions for the development of tourist infrastructure and attract investments in the industry. The activities of the Program are also aimed at increasing the effectiveness of promoting the national tourist product in the

domestic and international markets, improving the personnel training system [1].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

In accordance with the implementation of the federal target program in Kalmykia, a “Concept for the development of ethno-cultural tourism in the Republic of Kalmykia for 2015-2018” was developed. The tools proposed by the Concept for implementing the federal target program are based on the active participation of public institutions in developing and implementing solutions for the formation of promising and successful tourist and recreational complexes.

The state program of the Republic of Kalmykia “Development of culture and tourism of the Republic of Kalmykia for 2013-2020” is aimed at the integrated development of the main activities in the field of culture, tourism and archival affairs.

In accordance with the program, 2 main priority levels have been identified:

- The first is measures to improve and modernize the infrastructure of the industry, reconstruct and construct new buildings, current and capital repairs of state institutions of culture, tourism and archival affairs;
- The second is the preservation of the unique historical and cultural heritage of the Kalmyk people, the development of the main areas of culture and tourism, the harmonization of interethnic and interfaith relations, the ethno-cultural development of the peoples of the Republic of Kalmykia, the protection and promotion of monuments of tangible and intangible cultural heritage, the development of artistic education and the implementation of personnel policy.
- The main goal of the Program is to increase the competitiveness of the tourist complex, which will be able to meet the needs of both Russian and foreign tourists.
- To achieve the main goal of the program, the following tasks were set:
- development of the tourist complex of the Russian Federation;
- improving the quality of tourist services provided;
- promotion of the tourist product in the global and domestic markets.
- It should be noted that the development of the tourist sphere of the Republic of Kalmykia has certain prospects for stimulating the development of the regional economy. The Ministry of Culture

of the Russian Federation has developed a program for the development of culture and tourism in Russia until 2020. The program is a series of measures, methods and instruments of state policy that ensure the achievement of priority objectives of the state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Attraction of investments from the federal budget and extrabudgetary sources will be carried out through the implementation of participation in federal target programs "Development of domestic and inbound tourism in the Russian Federation (2011-2018)", as well as "Development of culture and tourism of the Russian Federation (2013-2020)", the purpose of which is to increase the competitiveness of the domestic tourist market that meets the needs of Russian and foreign citizens in high-quality tourist

services, which is in line with the purpose of the Concept.

Effective development of the tourist complex in the region will increase the flow of tourists, the inflow of financial revenues to the economy of the republic, the growth of tax deductions to budgets of various levels, as well as a favorable impact on related sectors of the economy represented in the form of transport services, logistics, catering tourist complexes in rural settlements, etc. In addition, the development of tourism in Kalmykia will form the prerequisites for the preservation and revival of cultural and natural heritage sites [2].

Analysis of the structure of cultural institutions from 2013-2018. Table 1 shows that the number of theaters, museums and libraries can fully satisfy both the needs of the population of the region and potential tourists.

Table 1: Cultural institutions structure of the Republic of Kalmykia

Indicators	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Professional theaters	4	4	3	2	2	2
including:						
Drama, Comedy, Musical	3	3	2	2	2	2
Children, young viewer	1	1	1	-	-	-
Museums	5	5	1	1	1	1
Libraries	178	172	156	149	149	148
Institutions of cultural and leisure type	203	175	155	150	150	149

The insignificant decrease in the number of cultural institutions in recent years is due to the trend of development and distribution of the Internet, and, consequently, access to electronic resources of literature, theatrical productions and museum exhibits. In addition, modern tourist and recreational resources of the republic are presented:

- 19 natural sites of regional and federal significance;

- 15 hunting farms;
- 200 objects of historical and cultural heritage;
- 195 historical monuments;
- 7 monuments of architecture;
- 2 monuments of monumental art.

SWOT analysis will help analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the development of the tourism industry in Kalmykia (Table 2).

Table 2: SWOT-analysis of tourism development in Republic of Kalmykia

Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
Advantageous geographical position of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Favorable climatic conditions, the proximity of the river. Volga and the Caspian Sea. Original national cultural and historical potential. Unique, pronounced Buddhist flavor in Europe. Stable geopolitical and ecological situation. Availability and implementation of a regional tourism development program. Availability of the international airport in Elista	Insufficient awareness of the population of the Russian Federation on the possibilities of tourism activities of the republic. Insufficient infrastructure of the tourism industry. Problems with water supply in the republic, especially with the quality of drinking water. Application of old tourist technologies. Low percentage of tourism in the Gross Regional Product. Population outflow to other regions of the country due to lack of jobs. Lack of passenger train communication with regions of the country
Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
The presence of an unoccupied working-age population and the possibility of its involvement in the field of activity. Creation and development of a special economic zone of tourist and recreational type. Construction of infrastructure facilities and production. Improving the quality and safety of travel services	Untimely financing from budgets of various levels. The overall unfavorable macroeconomic situation, which caused a decline in real profits. Possible entry into the market of large tour operators, which will lead to curtailing the activities of tourism subjects of the republic

The richness and color of culture, historical monuments, folk traditions and ethnic uniqueness of the Republic of Kalmykia make it possible to include this region among the favorable ones for the development of ethno-cultural tourism [5].

In addition, the positive dynamics of growth in demand for the provision of tourism services in recent years characterizes the level of attractiveness and opportunities of the republic.

In general, the implementation of the provisions of the "Tourism" sub-program and the federal target program "Development of domestic and inbound tourism" for 2013-2018 held in accordance with the planned schedule of tasks (figure 1). For example, projects of tourist routes are being created, restoration of cultural and historical attractions is underway, a visa regime for foreign tourists is being facilitated, work on tax breaks for participants of the tourist market has already been completed [6].

Figure 1: Dynamics of tourist-recreational services development in 2014 - 2018

The territory of the Republic of Kalmykia combines a unique set of historical cultural, geographical and natural heritage. An important factor is the comfortable geographical location and features of the Buddhist culture in the European part of Russia. The region has great potential to create an active tourist industry and such areas as gastronomic, cultural, religious, ecological, family, cultural and educational tourism [7].

CONCLUSION:

Thus, revealing the tourist potential, the republic will get the opportunity to develop business in this direction, which is an important factor in the process of attracting new money flows and investments in the economy. It is the development of the tourism industry on the territory of the Republic of Kalmykia that can serve as one of the tools to combat major

socio-economic problems, ensure the creation of new jobs and expand the sphere of small and medium-sized businesses, lead to a reduction in the outflow of able-bodied young people, as well as provide prerequisites for improved competitiveness. economy of the region.

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